

seedlings with all roots removed by cutting at ground level showed increased mortality and yield reduction. Seedlings with 98% roots removed could be used at higher numbers/hill to counteract hill mortality.

IET6155 and IET6148 had significantly lower hill mortality under all levels of root damage, indicating their ability for quick establishment. □

Source-sink relationship at postflowering of rices under low light stress

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We screened cultivars for tolerance for low light during ripening and assessed

the source-sink relationship. Seedlings (25 d old) of 15 early- and medium-duration rice varieties were transplanted at 10- × 10-cm spacing. Four uniform tillers/hill were selected at flowering. Five hills each were subjected to normal light and low light (50% normal), with two replications. The desired light intensity was obtained by covering the rice canopy with a wooden screen fitted on iron frames and adjusting the distance between the slats.

Data on shade index (ratio of grain yield under low and normal light) indicate variation in varietal response (see table). Under low light, Co 41, Archana, Jalgaon 5, and Ptb 10 showed about 50% yield reduction. Other varieties had higher yield reductions. Shading during ripening increased sterility and decreased 1,000-grain weight. Ratna, Pusa 33, Indira, and

Pallavi had more than 85% sterility.

The product of leaf area and solar radiation or leaf area and photosynthetic rate at flowering was taken as the source of carbohydrate. The product of spikelet number and test weight was taken as the sink.

The correlation between source and sink under normal light was positive and significant ($r = 0.76^{**a}$ and 0.64^{**b}), resulting in good correlation between source and grain yield ($r = 0.54^*$). Those relationships were observed under low light.

Under low light, the association between stem weight ratio at flowering and yield was positive ($r = 0.72^{**}$). The stem losses were higher under low light.

The balance of source and sink under natural light appears to be disturbed under low light stress, causing more stem loss. □

Influence of low light during ripening on yield and yield characters of 15 rice varieties. CRR, India.

Variety	Yield ^a (g)		Shading index	Grain no.		Stem loss (g) (flowering-harvest)		Sterility (%)		1000-grain wt (g)	
	100% light	50% light		Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light	Normal light	Low light
	Pusa 33	14.3		1.6	11	787	114	2.38	4.02	67.9	91.5
Co 41	13.4	7.9	59	764	546	0.42	4.71	53.8	58.0	17.5	14.4
Cauvery	11.7	4.2	36	572	281	0.47	6.25	71.7	73.0	20.4	14.9
Saket 4	12.2	3.8	31	611	231	0.92	3.24	57.3	76.6	19.9	16.2
Jalgaon 5	14.4	7.3	51	680	375	2.14	10.48	72.9	77.5	21.1	19.4
Ratna	11.1	0.8	9	628	55	5.36	6.48	61.8	93.0	17.7	15.1
ADT32	25.0	8.7	35	1206	546	2.21	3.38	42.5	62.6	20.7	15.8
Karikalan	17.6	7.5	43	742	364	2.40	8.38	34.7	51.8	23.7	20.6
Swarnaprabha	18.8	7.7	41	793	348	8.56	14.14	64.7	65.1	23.8	22.1
Ptb 10	19.3	9.2	47	771	388	5.30	8.57	29.6	62.2	25.1	23.7
Indira	11.3	2.0	17	551	136	1.68	3.57	70.4	86.2	20.5	14.5
CR157-190	14.5	3.1	22	683	176	4.08	7.28	63.8	83.1	21.3	17.8
Archana	11.2	6.4	58	569	369	5.32	9.90	65.1	70.5	19.7	17.5
IR36	15.7	3.9	25	725	219	1.01	4.79	59.0	80.0	21.6	17.6
Pallavi	12.8	2.3	18	635	140	1.02	1.73	55.9	87.5	20.1	16.2
Mean	14.9	5.1	33	714	286	2.88	6.48	58.1	74.6	20.8	17.8
LSD (0.05)											
Variety (V)	1.2		9	19		0.70		1.5		0.7	
Shading (S)	0.4			7		0.25		0.6		0.3	
V × S	1.7			27		0.99		2.2		1.0	

^aFrom 20 tillers.

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